

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17478232

Nutritional Health Information On Instagram And The Healthy Eating Habits Of Undergraduates

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ABSTRACT

With the rising prevalence of social media platforms, Instagram has emerged as a prominent source of health-related content, potentially influencing the nutritional choices of young adults. This study examines the influence of exposure to nutritional health information disseminated through Instagram on the eating habits of undergraduates in Anambra State. The main objective of the study was to investigate how exposure to Instagram based nutritional health information influences the eating habits of undergraduates in Anambra State focusing on the extent of exposure, sources of exposure, perceived credibility of information, perceived influence and relationship between exposure and adoption of healthy eating habits. The study was anchored on the media richness theory which provided the framework in understanding the study variables. Survey was used as the method of study using the questionnaire as an instrument for data collection. A multistage sampling procedure was employed to select 384 respondents for the study involving probability and nonprobability sampling methods from a population of 60,903 drawn from three universities in Anambra State including Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam and Paul University, Awka where the study was carried out. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results revealed that there is high exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram among the respondents of which influencers serve as their major sources of nutritional health information. The study also revealed that exposure to Instagram-based nutritional health information influence the dietary choices and habits of the respondents which result to the adoption of healthy eating habits such as food preferences, portion size and meal frequency. The study recommends that students should seek expert guidance when making significant changes to their diets by consulting with healthcare professionals or registered dietitians for personalized nutritional advice to ensure that their choices align with their individual health needs. The study also recommends that educational institutions should incorporate media literacy programs into their curriculum to equip undergraduate students with the skills to critically evaluate health information on social media platforms like Instagram.

Keywords: Nutrition, Health information, Instagram, Healthy Eating Habits

INTRODUCTION

The use of Instagram as a source of health and nutrition information has gained popularity among young adults globally including Nigerian students. According to a survey conducted by Pew Research Center, 71% of 18-24-year-olds in the US use Instagram as of 2019 (Anderson & Jiang, 2019). In Nigeria, a study by Digital 2021 found that as of January 2021, there were 4.9 million active Instagram users in Nigeria, with 64% of them belonging to the 18-34 age range (We are Social & Hootsuite, 2019). As such,

Instagram has become a platform where students can access nutritional health information that can influence their dietary habits. Instagram is flooded with health and fitness influencers and bloggers who provide nutrition-related information to their followers. These influencers post pictures and videos of their healthy meals, workout routines, and healthy lifestyles. As shown by Cvetkovic, Nikolic and Stojanović (2019), these posts are often accompanied by litany of emotional appeals, which can elicit positive emotional states and generate positive feelings toward healthy eating.

The use of Instagram by college students to access nutritional health information offers unique opportunities to engage them in healthy eating behaviors. A study has shown that Instagram users tend to perceive the platform as a trustworthy source of information and are more likely to adopt health behaviors promoted on the social network (Laroche et al., 2019). Thus, Instagram can be effectively used to promote healthy eating habits among students. Access to nutritional health information on Instagram provides students with the opportunity to gain knowledge and understanding of the nutrients and food groups necessary for a balanced diet. This information can drive changes in the dietary habits of students and positively impact their health outcomes (Frandsen & Madsen, 2017). The Instagram platform allows individuals to follow people or hashtags of their interest, making it easier for students to access and tailor information to their dietary preferences and needs. This customization provides an avenue for students to learn and adopt personalized healthy eating habits that fit their lifestyles.

Instagram is inundated with health and fitness influencers and bloggers who provide nutrition-related information to their followers. These influencers post pictures and videos of their healthy meals, workout routines, and healthy lifestyles. The pervasive issue of unhealthy eating habits among young adults represents a significant social problem with far-reaching consequences for individual well-being and public health. This demographic often faces a confluence of factors that contribute to poor dietary choices, including increased autonomy over food decisions, the influence of peer groups and social environments, time constraints due to academic or work pressures, and the accessibility of affordable yet nutrient-poor options. Diets high in processed foods, sugary beverages, and saturated fats, coupled with low consumption of fruits, vegetables, and whole grains, are increasingly common. These patterns are not isolated incidents but rather a widespread trend with the potential to lead to various health complications, including obesity, cardiovascular diseases, type 2 diabetes, and certain types of cancer, impacting their quality of life and future health outcomes.

The implications of these unhealthy eating habits extend beyond individual health, posing a considerable burden on healthcare systems and societal productivity. As young adults transition into later life stages, the cumulative effects of poor nutrition can manifest in chronic diseases that require long-term management and care. Furthermore, the social and economic costs associated with reduced productivity and increased healthcare demands underscore the urgency of addressing the root causes of unhealthy eating behaviors in this population. Understanding the factors that shape their food choices and identifying effective strategies for promoting healthier dietary patterns are therefore critical from a public health perspective.

Instagram's emphasis on visual cues and aesthetics makes a healthy diet more marketable. As such, Instagram has the potential to create a cultural shift where individuals view healthy eating habits as fashionable, driving greater adoption among young adults (Pangborn & Pauwels, 2021). Social media platforms such as Instagram are essential sources of health, fitness, and wellness inspiration among young adults. According to a study by Mintel (2019), 71% of young adults are interested in learning about healthy meal ideas and recipes on social media platforms. Instagram's capacity to provide students with nutritious and healthy recipes and meal ideas is crucial, particularly for those with busy schedules. A study by Ting et al. (2021) shows that college students who follow nutritionists and dietitians on Instagram have higher dietary knowledge and a more positive perception of healthy eating behaviors. The study further shows that following healthy eating influencers promotes an attitude of pragmatism towards adopting healthy eating behaviors.

Instagram is beneficial because it allows individuals to follow people or hashtags of their interest, making it easier for Nigerian students to access and tailor information to their dietary preferences and needs. This customization provides an avenue for students to learn and adopt personalized healthy eating habits that

fit their lifestyles. Instagram's use of influencers in promoting health and nutritional information aligns with the health belief model, which posits that health behavior is shaped by an individual's perception of susceptibility and severity of a health condition and the perceived benefits and barriers to health behavior (Rosenstock, 2019). Influencers can elicit emotions that appeal to the health belief model, influencing Nigerian students to adopt healthy eating habits.

Instagram's social and connected nature allows users to connect with like-minded people and form online communities, providing Nigerian students with social support and motivation to adopt healthy eating habits. Students can connect with other users to share their progress, ask questions, and learn from others. This approach is effective in building and maintaining social networks, which have been shown to be positively associated with healthy eating habits in students (Quandt et al., 2015). Instagram exposes Nigerian students to a wide range of dietary and nutritional information, including alternative, cultural, and plant-based diets. For example, individuals following accounts such as *nigerian_vegan* and *plant based nigerian* can learn about vegan and plant-based meals. The platform can expose Nigerian students to non-traditional dietary choices and influence them in their choice of a healthy diet. This study, therefore, aimed to assess how exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram influence the healthy eating habits of undergraduate students in Anambra State.

Objectives of the Study

1. To ascertain the respondents' perceptions on the credibility of the nutritional information they are exposed to on Instagram.
2. To analyze the influence of Instagram-based nutritional health information on the dietary choices and habits of the respondents.

Theoretical Framework: Media Richness Theory

Media Richness Theory, proposed by Daft and Lengel in 1984, is a communication theory that emphasizes the capacity of different communication channels to effectively convey information. It classifies communication media into a continuum ranging from lean (low richness) to rich (high richness). Lean media, such as written text, lack the ability to convey non-verbal cues, while rich media, like face-to-face interactions, allow for the transmission of multiple cues and provide prompt feedback. This theory has gained renewed relevance in the digital age due to the proliferation of various communication platforms (Daft & Lengel, 1984). The choice of media depends on the nature of the message and the richness required for effective communication (Daft & Lengel, 1984).

According to Media Richness Theory, the choice of communication medium depends on the richness required for effective communication. On Instagram, users are exposed to various forms of nutritional health information, including images, videos, and text captions. The richness of these media varies, with videos and images being richer in conveying visual cues and context compared to text alone (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Rich media, such as visually appealing and informative infographics or videos about healthy eating, have the potential to enhance users' understanding of nutritional information. When individuals encounter rich content that provides visual cues and explanations, it can influence their comprehension of dietary recommendations and encourage healthier choices (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Media Richness Theory also suggests that rich media can have a more profound impact on behavior. In the context of Instagram, this means that visually engaging and informative posts about healthy eating are more likely to capture users' attention and motivate them to adopt healthier eating habits (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Rich media formats, such as interactive polls, quizzes, or live cooking demonstrations on Instagram, can facilitate user engagement. The ability to interact with content and receive real-time feedback aligns with the richness principle of the theory, potentially leading to a more meaningful and sustained influence on users' dietary choices (Epstein et al., 2018).

The theory's concept of media richness also intersects with the issue of filter bubbles on social media platforms. Users often encounter content that aligns with their existing dietary preferences and opinions, which can create echo chambers of like-minded dietary choices. Understanding how Instagram's algorithm-driven content personalization shapes users' exposure to nutritional information is essential (Johnson & Smith, 2019). Moreover, the algorithmic curation of content on Instagram plays a crucial role.

The platform uses algorithms to personalize content feeds based on user behavior and preferences, potentially reinforcing selective exposure tendencies. Users are more likely to encounter content that aligns with their existing beliefs about healthy eating (Epstein et al., 2018). Users are often primarily exposed to content that mirrors their existing dietary preferences and opinions. This can create echo chambers of like-minded dietary choices, further reinforcing existing habits and influencing students' eating behaviors (Johnson & Smith, 2019).

Media Richness Theory is relevant to this study as it offers a valuable framework for understanding how exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram influences the healthy eating habits of students. The theory's emphasis on the richness of communication channels provides insights into the effectiveness of different forms of content on the platform. Visual media, such as images and videos, play a crucial role in conveying nutritional information. Additionally, the algorithmic curation of content and the phenomenon of filter bubbles contribute to the dynamics of exposure. Understanding these factors is crucial for designing effective health communication strategies on social media platforms and promoting healthy eating habits among students.

Instagram as a Platform for the Dissemination of Nutritional Health Information

Instagram, a visual-centric social media platform, has emerged as a powerful tool for the dissemination of nutritional information. With its emphasis on visual content, Instagram offers a unique avenue for health professionals, dietitians, influencers, and organizations to share knowledge about nutrition and healthy eating practices. Instagram's visual nature makes it an ideal platform for conveying nutritional information. Users are drawn to visually appealing content, and the use of images and videos allows for the presentation of healthy food choices, meal ideas, and nutritional facts in an engaging manner (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Instagram influencers, particularly those in the health and wellness niche, play a significant role in disseminating nutritional information. These influencers often share their personal dietary journeys, recipes, and tips for healthy living, influencing the choices of their followers (Hsu et al., 2019).

Nutritional experts, dietitians, and healthcare organizations use Instagram to share educational content. They post infographics, charts, and informative captions to impart knowledge about portion control, macronutrients, micronutrients, and the benefits of various foods (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Instagram is a treasure trove of healthy recipe ideas. Users frequently share step-by-step tutorials through images and videos, making it easy for others to replicate nutritious meals and snacks. This aspect aligns with the practical application of nutritional information (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Personal stories of health transformations through dietary changes are often shared on Instagram. Users showcase their journeys toward healthier eating habits, providing inspiration and motivation to others who seek to improve their diets (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020).

Challenges and trends related to nutrition often gain traction on Instagram. Examples include the "30-Day Clean Eating Challenge" or "Meatless Monday," which encourage users to adopt specific dietary habits and share their progress, fostering a sense of community (Hsu et al., 2019). Researchers and institutions use Instagram to disseminate findings from nutrition-related studies. They present scientific evidence on topics such as the health benefits of specific foods or the impact of diet on chronic conditions, making research more accessible to the public (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). Infographics are a powerful tool on Instagram for condensing complex nutritional information into digestible visuals. These graphics can effectively communicate the nutritional content of foods, dietary guidelines, and health statistics (Hsu et al., 2019).

Instagram's interactive features, including polls, quizzes, and live broadcasts, allow for real-time engagement with nutritional content. Dietitians can use these tools to gauge users' knowledge, answer questions, and provide personalized advice (Epstein et al., 2018). Instagram's algorithm-driven content personalization influences users' exposure to nutritional information. The platform tailors users' feeds based on their interactions, potentially reinforcing existing dietary preferences and introducing them to new ideas (Johnson & Smith, 2019). Trust in the source of nutritional information is paramount. Users are more likely to engage with content shared by sources they perceive as credible, such as registered

dietitians or recognized health organizations. Building trust is crucial for the effective dissemination of nutritional information (Lee & Lee, 2020).

Instagram's global reach allows nutritional information to transcend geographical boundaries. Health professionals and organizations can disseminate content worldwide, reaching diverse audiences with culturally relevant dietary advice (Hsu et al., 2019). Instagram is frequently used for health campaigns and awareness initiatives. Organizations leverage the platform to promote events, challenges, and campaigns related to nutrition, encouraging users to participate and share their experiences (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020). The platform thrives on user-generated content. Individuals often share their meal creations, dietary tips, and product recommendations. This user-generated content adds authenticity to the dissemination of nutritional information (Hsu et al., 2019). Instagram allows for the use of various content formats, including carousel posts, stories, IGTV videos, and live broadcasts. This diversity enables content creators to tailor their messages to different audience preferences and engagement styles (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020).

Users can engage with nutritional content through likes, comments, direct messages, and sharing. This two-way interaction fosters a sense of community and encourages further dissemination of nutritional information (Epstein et al., 2018). Instagram's mobile app ensures that nutritional information is accessible to users on-the-go. Whether in a grocery store or a restaurant, users can quickly access dietary tips, healthy recipes, and food product reviews (Hsu et al., 2019). The platform's social features, such as following, tagging, and sharing, create a sense of accountability. Users may feel more motivated to make healthier food choices when they share their dietary goals and achievements with their followers (Smith & Pettigrew, 2020).

Among the various social media platforms, it is believed that Instagram has better feature that helps the platform to share a more appealing picture especially as it relates to food and lifestyle posts. As a result of the aforementioned, Instagram today has become one of the major platforms for the dissemination of appealing nutritional information by different sources. Research (Adamski et. al, 2020, Moorman et. al, 2020), has shown that college students and young adults mainly access their nutrition advice and information from social media and visual platform including Instagram have become the most trusted source of nutritional information among the youth (Jackson et. al, 2019). Given credence to the above submission, Carrotteet. al, (2015) revealed that Instagram has become a platform for accessing diet and fitness information for young adults.

According to Bourke et. al, (2019) Instagram offers its users personal connectedness through hashtags when its users share personal experiences and create support networks for various topics. Personal connectedness can add to motivations for using Instagram for nutrition advice because people value the personal experiences provided by 'real people' and describe nutrition information from Instagram as more relevant to and personalized than general nutrition advice. According to the research of Cavusoglu and Demirbağ-Kaplan (2017), the use of hashtags is a useful promotional tool on Instagram and that #healthy is commonly associated with four themes that consumers often align with the hashtag, relating to the concept of lifestyle, namely fitness, food, feelings and fashion. This goes to say that nutritional-related hashtags are common on Instagram.

Also, the promotion of healthy and conscious food products on Instagram can be reinforced with the use of social media influencers (SMIs). Several nutritional, food influencers have emerged on Instagram, hence, the terms 'insta-norm' and 'ethno-nutritionism' were created to describe the robust of nutrition posts happening on Instagram (Atkinson, 2011; Holland & Tiggeman, 2016). By developing a level of trust, and sharing their life experiences, influencers impact the ideas that consumers have about products, but also influence their purchasing behavior. In the case of food products, the promotion of certain items by influencers will not only increase the credibility and impact the brand image, but also contribute to higher visibility and customer reach (Uzunoglu & Misci Kip, 2014; Liu, et al. 2015, cited by Klassen et al. 2018). In the same manner, individuals post and repost content related to food and wellness lifestyle on Instagram, such acts facilitate consumer-to-consumer conversations and enable followers to contribute to the promotion of the message or brand (Mangold & Faulds, 2009).

The last (but by no means least) advantage of Instagram as a promotional channel resides in its ability to advertise messages to the most likely interested target (Belch, Belch, Kerr & Powell, 2012). Indeed, thanks to the algorithm systems developed by the platform, followers received ads that presumably reflect their content and interests. In other words, food brands have more chance of reaching the target willing to buy their products. Therefore, the promotion will be more effective as the ads will be relevant in the eyes of the users (Belch, Belch, Kerr & Powell, 2012).

As powerful as social media and Instagram could be as a platform of nutritional information dissemination, there are concerns about the quality of information accessed through the social media platforms including Instagram. With enormous quantity of web pages, online services and applications related to health on different social media platforms, it can be hard to find high quality and trusted health information (Fox & Jones, 2010). Similarly, social media is a washed with unregulated information and advice on health, this further raises serious concerns on the reliability of health information on the platforms (Arunachalam, 1998). Abadi and Sheikhtaheri (2015) has identified inaccurate medical advices, adverse health consequences, negative health behaviors and information overload as potential dangers of social media for health information.

In health communication the reliability of information is important for the reader. Readers need to know what the source of the information is and that it is based on scientific evidence. However, on social media, source identification can be complex because of the many the sharers of the message and sometimes the difficulty of identifying the originator of the message. This phenomenon has given rise to the proliferation of fake information from unknown sources some of which are machine or software enabled designed for the purpose of massive distribution of fake information including health contents (Buchanan, 2020).

In another dimension, Schein, Wilson and Keelan (2011) opined that Social media decentralizes the sources of information even more making the quality of the information on this websites vary. These conflicts of interest and other sources of erroneous information effect health communication on social media (Youngh, 2011). Errors in information can then reach the public and can have a negative effect on the health decisions of individuals, as was seen with a case of Ebola in Nigeria where many people engaged in the ritual of bathing with salt as protection measure and in the recent case of Covid 19 vaccination promotion which has attracted some resistant due to scores of misinformation in many social media platforms (Maikomo& Shadrach, 2021). Obi-Ani, Anikwenze and Isiani (2020) corroborate that what is worrisome with the engagement of social media especially in the fight against Covid 19 pandemic in Nigeria and indeed the global community is how to sieve authentic information from an avalanche of half-truths and false information available on social media networks. In the same vein, Kington, Arnesen, Chou, Curry, Lazer and Villarruel (2021) states that the pandemic (COVID-19) has demonstrated the potentially malign outcomes of social media. Misinformation about the disease spread through social media and other online forums—often fueled by politicization of scientific information and has considerably harmed the adoption of recommended prevention and control behaviors and has decreased support for vital policies, such as vaccination.

According to Naseri and Sheikhtaheri (2015) also argues that social media often raise privacy concerns, users often worry about how their personal health information can be used and disclosed outright by certain platforms, there is also the possibility that personal information of users can be stolen and sold by unauthorized entities who hack social media and health services websites. Another concern raised regarding social media is the fact that technically, users do not have to proactively seek information that confirms their beliefs or need; algorithms used by Social media platforms and other web platforms often recommend content on the basis of users' past behaviors and expressed interests, leading to passive or incidental exposure. In the case of low-quality health information, such reinforcement loops can be harmful (Yang, 2017). However, Instagram serves as a dynamic and influential platform for the dissemination of nutritional information. Its visual nature, user-generated content, interactive features, and global reach make it a powerful tool for health professionals, dietitians, influencers, and organizations to share knowledge, inspire dietary changes, and foster healthier eating habits among users.

Correlation between Exposure to Nutritional Health Information on Instagram and Healthy Eating Habits among Students

In recent years, social media platforms have emerged as influential sources of health-related information, particularly in the context of nutritional health. Among these platforms, Instagram stands out as a prominent channel for disseminating dietary advice, recipes, and nutritional facts. Instagram's visual nature and widespread popularity have made it a preferred platform for sharing images and videos related to food, nutrition, and healthy lifestyles (Booth, 2019). With over one billion active users worldwide, Instagram offers a vast reach for nutritional information dissemination (Instagram, 2021). Recent studies indicate that social media platforms have become primary sources of health-related information, especially among younger demographics (Figueiredo et al., 2019). The accessibility and ease of sharing content on Instagram make it an ideal platform for health influencers, dietitians, and fitness enthusiasts to reach a broad audience. Instagram offers a convenient platform for undergraduates to access a wide array of nutritional information. This accessibility allows them to easily explore healthy eating options and dietary recommendations (Smith, 2020).

Visual content on Instagram, including images of nutritious meals and cooking tutorials, plays a significant role in shaping individuals' perceptions of healthy eating (Tiggemann & Slater, 2014). Exposure to appealing visuals may lead to increased motivation to adopt similar dietary practices. The visual nature of Instagram content has a profound impact on its viewers. High-quality images of nutritious meals and visually appealing presentations can inspire undergraduates to adopt healthier eating habits (Kite et al., 2018). One critical factor in the effectiveness of Instagram as a source of nutritional health information is the perceived credibility of influencers. Research suggests that trust in influencers' expertise and authenticity strongly influences their impact on followers' behavior (Freberg et al., 2011). Thus, the qualifications and credentials of health influencers on Instagram are crucial. Many Instagram accounts focused on health and nutrition provide educational content, explaining the benefits of various foods, debunking myths, and offering evidence-based advice (Smith et al., 2016).

Exposure to such content may enhance individuals' knowledge about nutrition and encourage healthier food choices. Social media platforms like Instagram create spaces where users can form communities around shared interests, including healthy eating. Studies have shown that social norms and peer influence play a significant role in shaping dietary behaviors (Brenner, 2020). Positive reinforcement from peers and influencers can motivate individuals to adopt healthier eating habits. Influencers, often seen as relatable figures, play a pivotal role in shaping dietary preferences. When credible nutrition experts or registered dietitians endorse healthy eating practices, undergraduates are more likely to trust and adopt their recommendations (Parker et al., 2019). Undergraduates are also influenced by their peers' behaviors and preferences. If healthy eating practices are promoted within their social circles on Instagram, it can establish positive social norms around nutrition (Becker et al., 2017).

Instagram is replete with food bloggers and influencers who share recipes for nutritious meals. Research suggests that exposure to such content can lead to increased preparation of healthy dishes at home (Neumark-Sztainer et al., 2017). This, in turn, can contribute to the establishment of healthier eating patterns. Instagram provides a platform for individuals with specific dietary needs or allergies to connect and share information. This can be particularly beneficial for students with dietary restrictions, as they can find support and learn about suitable alternatives through the platform (Serrano et al., 2019). While Instagram is a valuable source of nutritional health information, it is not without risks. Studies have highlighted the prevalence of misinformation and pseudoscientific claims on social media platforms, which can potentially lead to misguided dietary choices (Tang et al., 2019). It is essential for users to critically evaluate the content they encounter. Several longitudinal studies have investigated the lasting effects of exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram. Findings suggest that consistent exposure to accurate and evidence-based information can lead to sustained improvements in dietary habits (Turner-McGrievy et al., 2019).

Instagram's global reach exposes undergraduates to diverse cultural dietary practices, allowing them to incorporate elements of different cuisines into their own eating habits (Willett, 2017). Exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram can increase awareness about the importance of a balanced

diet and educate undergraduates about the nutritional value of different foods (Turner-McGrievy et al., 2019). Instagram can serve as a source of motivation for undergraduates aiming to achieve specific health and fitness goals. Regular exposure to fitness and nutrition content can reinforce their commitment to healthy eating (Bélanger-Gravel et al., 2019). It is crucial to acknowledge that not all nutritional information on Instagram is reliable. Misinformation and the promotion of fad diets can lead to unhealthy eating patterns and disordered eating behaviors among undergraduates (Holland & Tiggemann, 2016). Exposure to evidence-based nutritional advice on Instagram can empower undergraduates to take control of their dietary choices and enhance their confidence in making healthier food selections (Chen & Wilkosz, 2019).

Regular exposure to content that reinforces healthy eating habits can lead to sustained behavior change. Over time, this can contribute to the development of a long-term pattern of healthy eating (Holland et al., 2018). Instagram facilitates social comparison, which can have both positive and negative effects on body image and eating habits. It is important to monitor the impact of such comparisons on undergraduates' well-being (Perloff, 2014). Incorporating evidence-based nutritional education within undergraduate curricula can complement the positive effects of Instagram exposure and further promote healthy eating habits (Vézina-Im et al., 2017).

Instagram serves as a powerful platform for disseminating nutritional health information and has the potential to positively influence the eating habits of students. The visual nature of Instagram, coupled with the educational content provided by credible influencers, fosters an environment conducive to the adoption of healthier dietary choices. However, users must exercise critical thinking to discern accurate information from potentially misleading content. Overall, Instagram represents a significant tool in promoting nutritional health awareness and fostering healthier eating habits among students. Thus, the correlation between exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram and healthy eating habits among undergraduates is a complex interplay of various psychological, social, and informational factors. While Instagram holds potential as a platform for promoting healthy eating, it is important to be mindful of the potential pitfalls, including the spread of misinformation. Continued research in this area will provide valuable insights for developing effective strategies to leverage social media for improved dietary behaviors among undergraduates.

RESEARCH METHOD

For this study, the survey research method was adopted to investigate how exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram influences the healthy eating habits of undergraduates in Anambra State. By using this method, the researcher sampled the opinions of subset of undergraduate students in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam and Paul University, Awka all in Anambra State. Therefore, the population of the study was made up of all undergraduate students of the Nnamdi Azikiwe University (NAU) Awka, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University (COOU) Igbariam, and Paul University Awka. According to the Students' Affairs Departments of the three Universities, their combined students' population as at July 2022 was 60,903. The breakdown of this population shows that NAU has 38,981 students, COOU has 21,320 students and Paul University has 602 students. A sample of 380 undergraduate students who are exposed to nutritional health information on Instagram was selected for the study. This sample was arrived at using a table of sample size determination developed by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The table establishes sample sizes against their corresponding population. The multistage sampling technique was adopted for this study with the application of randomization and purposive sampling.

Stage One: The researcher used purposive sampling technique to select Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka and Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam Campus. This is because the two universities are the only federal and state universities in Anambra state which is the study area.

Stage Two: The researcher adopted random sampling without replacement method to select one private school in Anambra State, which was Paul University, Awka.

Stage Three: In each of the selected universities, two faculties were selected for the study through simple random without replacement method. This procedure yielded faculties of Social Science and Arts for

NAU, Social Sciences and Management for COOU, and Management and Social Sciences for Paul University.

Stage Four: The researcher also used simple random without replacement method to select two departments each from the selected faculties for study. This procedure produced Mass communication and Sociology, Theatre Arts and English Language from the faculties of Social Sciences and Arts of NAU, Political Science, Criminology, Accountancy and Banking and Finance from COOU; and Philosophy, Sociology, Marketing and Accountancy from Paul University.

The researcher adopted Proportionate Allocation Formula to assign copies of questionnaire that were distributed to the respondents accordingly. This is shown below:

Nnamdi Azikiwe University	$\frac{38,981 \times 380}{60,903}$	= 243
COOU	$\frac{21,320 \times 380}{60,903}$	= 133
Paul University Awka	$\frac{602 \times 380}{60,903}$	= 4

Table 1: Universities Population and Sample Size drawn

Institution	Population	Faculty	Department	No. of Students sampled	Proportionate Sample Allocation
NAU	38,981	Social Sciences	Mass Com	61	243
			Sociology	61	
		Arts	Theatre Arts	61	
			English Lang.	60	
COOU	21,320	Social Sciences	Political Science	34	133
			Criminology	33	
		Management	Accountancy	33	
			Banking & Finance	33	
Paul University	602	Social Sciences	Philosophy	1	4
			Sociology	1	
		Management	Marketing	1	
			Accountancy	1	
Total	60,903				380

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Research Question One: *What is the respondents’ perceptions on the credibility of the nutritional health information they are exposed to on Instagram?*

Table 2: Respondents’ Perceptions on the Credibility of the Nutritional Health Information on Instagram

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Credible	245	69.00
Not Credible	68	19.00
Can’t Say	42	12.00
Total	360	100.00

Table 2 shows respondents’ responses to research question three. Data reveals that majority of the respondents (69%, n=245) perceived the nutritional health information they are exposed to on Instagram as credible as the information helped them to make informed decision towards their healthy eating habit. Also, 19% (n=68) said that they do not perceive the information as credible as most of it are coming from influencers who may pay less attention to the authenticity and trustworthiness of the information while 12% (n=42) indicated that they can’t say. The implication of data on Table 7 is the majority of the respondents perceive the nutritional health information they are exposed to on Instagram as credible as the information helped them to make informed decision towards their healthy eating habit.

Research Question Two: *How does Instagram-based nutritional health information influence the dietary choices and habits of the respondents?*

Table 3: Influence of Instagram-based Nutritional Health Information

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Changes in food preferences	55	15.00
Portion sizes	50	14.00
Meal frequency	46	13.00
All of the above	204	57.00
Total	355	100.00

Table 3 shows respondents’ responses to research question four. Data reveals that majority of the respondents (57%, n=204) indicated exposure to Instagram-based nutritional health information influence the dietary choices and habits as it results to changes in their food preferences, portion size and meal frequency. The implication of data on Table 8 is that exposure to Instagram-based nutritional health information influence the dietary choices and habits in their food preferences, portion size and meal frequency.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings from research question one revealed that the majority of the respondents perceive the nutritional health information they are exposed to on Instagram as credible as the information helped them to make informed decision towards their healthy eating habit. This supports the conclusions of Laroche et al., (2019) has shown that Instagram users tend to perceive the platform as a trustworthy source of information and are more likely to adopt health behaviors promoted on the social network. Individuals tend to perceive certain accounts as more credible based on the credentials, experience, or qualifications of the content creator. Registered dietitians, nutritionists, and healthcare professionals are often considered more trustworthy sources (Sylvetsky et al., 2020). The number of likes, comments, and shares a post receives can influence its perceived credibility. High engagement rates may suggest that the content is well-received and therefore, trustworthy (Fardouly et al., 2015). The visual appeal of a post can impact its perceived credibility. Well-designed graphics, professional imagery, and cohesive branding may lead individuals to trust the information presented (Brown et al., 2019). Content creators who are transparent about their qualifications, affiliations, and sources of information tend to be viewed as more credible. Authenticity builds trust with the audience (Leitschuh et al., 2019).

The findings from research question two shows that exposure to Instagram-based nutritional health information influence the dietary choices and habits in their food preferences, portion size and meal frequency. This finding was solidified by the test of the null hypothesis where the calculated mean value, X , was 3.60 which was greater than the decision point value of 3.0 by a difference of 0.60. It shows that $X = 3.60 > 3.0$ hence, the null hypothesis, H_0 , was rejected and its alternative, H_1 , was accepted. It implies, therefore that Instagram-based nutritional health information significantly influence the dietary choices and habits of the respondents. This supports the conclusions of Aransiola, Adeyele & Oyewusi (2020) shows that Instagram and other social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter can influence the dietary behavior of Nigerian undergraduate students. The study found that most of the students seek nutritional information on fast foods and snacks, but still, the percentage of those seeking information on healthy foods is significant. A study by Chima, Drayton & Eke (2020) shows that Nigerian students use Instagram to access nutritional information, but access is limited by internet connectivity issues, lack of data subscription, and inadequate knowledge of influencers.

From the discussion, Selective Exposure Theory provided a valuable framework for understanding how students engage with nutritional health information on platforms like Instagram. It sheds light on the role of confirmation bias, algorithmic curation, and filter bubbles in shaping exposure to dietary content. Also, Media Richness Theory offered a valuable framework for understanding how exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram influences the healthy eating habits of students. The theory's emphasis on the richness of communication channels provides insights into the effectiveness of different forms of content on the platform. Visual media, such as images and videos, play a crucial role in conveying nutritional information.

Summary

This research investigates the influence of exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram on the dietary habits of undergraduate students in Anambra State, Nigeria. The students of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University and Paul University were selected to form the area of study and respondents were drawn from the various faculties and departments in the institution. The study aimed to discern whether the exposure to health-related content on Instagram has a significant influence on the eating choices and behaviors of young adults. The selective exposure theory and the media richness theory were the theoretical anchorage of the study. The research employed the survey research method with a structured questionnaire administered to a sample of 374 undergraduate students from various institutions in Anambra State, The study's quantitative component analyzes the frequency and nature of nutritional health content consumption on Instagram, as well as its correlation with participants' dietary preferences and practices. The following findings were made:

1. Respondents perceive the nutritional health information they are exposed to on Instagram as credible as the information helped them to make informed decision towards their healthy eating habit.
2. Exposure to Instagram-based nutritional health information influence the dietary choices and habits in their food preferences, portion size and meal frequency.

CONCLUSION

This research provides valuable insights into the influence of exposure to nutritional health information on Instagram on the dietary habits of undergraduate students in Anambra State. The findings underscore the significance of social media platforms, particularly Instagram, as powerful sources of health-related information for young adults. The study revealed that while Instagram serves as a conduit for increased awareness of healthy eating habits, its impact on actual dietary behavior is nuanced. Some students reported positive shifts towards healthier choices, while others encountered challenges in discerning reliable information from the abundance of content available. This research provides critical insights into the role of Instagram as a medium for conveying nutritional health information and its subsequent influence on the dietary behaviors of undergraduates in Anambra State. The findings emphasize the importance of targeted and accurate content creation, as well as the need for public health campaigns to leverage social media platforms for disseminating reliable nutritional information. Overall, this research

underscores the dynamic interplay between social media exposure and dietary habits among undergraduate students. It provides a foundation for future interventions and educational programs aimed at fostering a culture of informed and healthy eating habits in the age of digital information dissemination. By doing so, we can positively impact the long-term health and well-being of young adults in Anambra State and beyond.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research findings, the researcher, therefore, made the following recommendations:

1. Health authorities and educational institutions should collaborate to develop and implement comprehensive nutrition education initiatives tailored to the needs and preferences of undergraduate students. These programs can cover topics such as the basics of nutrition, meal planning, and the importance of balanced diets.
2. Health authorities should actively promote and endorse reputable, evidence-based sources of nutritional information on social media platforms like Instagram. This can include partnerships with credible influencers and health experts to disseminate accurate and science-backed information.
3. Encourage the creation of supportive and informative online communities on Instagram where students can share their experiences, challenges, and successes in adopting healthier eating habits. Peer support can play a crucial role in reinforcing positive dietary choices.
4. Students should seek expert guidance when making significant changes to their diets by consulting with healthcare professionals or registered dietitians for personalized nutritional advice to ensure that their choices align with their individual health needs.

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